

APPENDIX 1. METHODOLOGICAL EXPLANATION

Butkevičienė, J., & Židonis, Ž., *From Hype to Meaning: Sensemaking in Blockchain Adoption* (in press).

(GIOIA APPROACH, Analysis and Coding Process)

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1. Overview

This appendix complements the methodological section of the chapter by Butkevičienė, J., & Židonis, Ž., *From Hype to Meaning: Sensemaking in Blockchain Adoption* (in press). It provides a detailed explanation of the data analysis and coding process conducted using the Gioia methodology. It focuses exclusively on the data analysis and coding process, following the Gioia methodology for inductive qualitative research. For details on research design, sampling, and data collection, please refer to the main chapter.

2. Sample

Data were collected through semi-structured interviews with 20 participants, including industry specialists, IT researchers, developers, and business managers from Lithuania, a member state of the European Union with a consistent regulatory framework. Employing purposeful sampling (Patton, 1990), individuals were chosen based on their extensive professional or research experience in blockchain technology, each possessing a minimum of five years of relevant experience. All participants held roles with international exposure, offering a diverse range of globally informed viewpoints.

Interviews, conducted between 2023 and 2024, lasted 30–60 minutes, were recorded, transcribed verbatim, and analysed inductively. The interviews were conducted in 2023 and 2024, with each session lasting between 30 to 60 minutes. All interviews were recorded and transcribed in full, and the empirical data were coded. The informants' language is presented in its original form and has not been edited for grammar or style.

Table 1. Summary of informants

Informant	Role/responsibility in the organisation	Company type and/or area of expertise	Experience
A	Chief Researcher	Research institution, Data science and digital technologies	7
B	Chief Delivery Officer (CDO)	Web3 and blockchain development, consultancy and acceleration services	5

C	Blockchain developer	Freelancer, Blockchain-based solutions development	8
D	Project Manager	Research institution, FinTech & Blockchain projects	5
E	Blockchain developer	Blockchain development and research lab. Development and evaluation Web3 and new generic blockchain concepts across industries	6
F	Chief Researcher	Research institution, Data science and digital technologies	7
G	CEO	Blockchain development and research lab. Web3, Blockchain, AI solutions	8
H	Blockchain Solutions Architect	Freelancer, Web3 and Blockchain-based solutions development	6
I	Corporate IT systems team lead	MNE, Banking technologies	20
J	CEO, IT service provider-	MNE, Digital platforms and cloud solutions, technology and blockchain applications provider	18
K	R&D and CIO- corporate IT systems management and cyber security	MNE, Aviation industry, Digital technologies, platform and cloud solutions, supply chain platforms	26
L	CEO, Fintech and Blockchain Solutions	MNE, Digital banking and DeFi Solutions	9
M	Head of FinCrime, Senior Compliance officer	MNE, Fintech & Blockchain solutions	17
N	Chief Information Officer	SME, Blockchain architect, Defi analyst	12
O	Head of the department, Fintech legislation unit	Ministry, Government official	20
P	Head of the department	Regulatory institution	8
R	Deputy chair	Regulatory institution	16
S	Deputy director	Supervisory institution, AML and financial investigation	22
T	Investor	Venture capital	20
U	CEO, Business Angel	Technology & Cyber security solutions	20

3. Analytical Process

Our study adopts a Grounded theory approach, often referred to as the *Gioia methodology* for inductive, interpretive research (Gioia, Corley & Hamilton, 2013), which is particularly suited for exploring emergent technologies and new organizational phenomena. We began from a position of theoretical openness, seeking to generate a grounded explanation of how actors make sense of blockchain adoption and how meaning evolves beyond the initial phase of technological hype.

Data analysis followed an iterative and systematic process typical of the Gioia approach. Each interview was first transcribed verbatim. Both authors then independently conducted first-order coding, assigning informant-centric, *in vivo* labels that reflected the participants' own language and sensemaking expressions (e.g., "single source of truth," "pilot to prove value"). During this stage, we paid special attention to cues that triggered sensemaking, identity references, cognitive framings of disruption, and projected actions related to blockchain adoption.

Through iterative comparison and analysis between data and emerging ideas, we grouped similar first-order codes into second-order themes - researcher-centric categories that began to reveal underlying patterns of *perceived benefits, challenges, opportunities and novelty-Ecosystem readiness frame*, which derived from the data (please see Appendix 2). Weekly meetings were used to discuss discrepancies. Next, we abstracted the second-order themes into aggregate dimensions. Theme stability was achieved after the 16th interview, and four additional interviews confirmed theoretical saturation. To enhance credibility, we conducted findings checks with three participants, ensuring that our interpretations resonated with the lived experiences of industry experts.

The study's interview protocol comprised four main groups of semi-structured questions designed to address the research objectives:

- A) Opportunities for blockchain technology in the current business environment.
- B) Advantages of using blockchain.
- C) Difficulties and challenges associated with blockchain integration.
- D) A blockchain adoption in supply-chain management.

4. CODING SCHEME

The structure of the coding process is illustrated below.

Figure 1. Data structure – - Scheme of Coding

5. DATA CODING TABLES

The tables below provide representative examples of how first-order concepts were grouped into second-order themes and aggregate dimensions.

Table 2. Perceived Benefits of Blockchain Adoption Frame (Coding)

First order codes	Selected evidence
Viewing information as a chance to build new relationships	
Transparency	The use of blockchain technology in the international supply chain would provide several advantages, but transparency is fundamental-since all participants in the chain would see real-time and irreplaceably fixed records of transactions, ensuring visibility and reliability of all actions (C)
Traceability	Human error is a factor that, again, blockchain helps minimise, since actions are always traceable. Knowing that there's no way to change the record or to somehow adjust it without knowing it for others, people act more responsibly. Blockchain technology makes it easier to track down all the time, to trace it or see that there is something wrong. (G) To see the transaction for the supervisory institution, you already need specialised tools, chain analysis tools, and special gadgets, which are also expensive and require competencies. (S)
Trust	The use of blockchain technology in the international supply chain would really provide several advantages: transparency is fundamental since all participants in the chain would see real-time and irreplaceably fixed transaction records, ensuring visibility and reliability of all actions. This increases trust and simplifies audit processes. (C) It would significantly speed up all the process and would not require a third party or significantly reduce the intervention of a third party in a certain check to find out a lot of demo fault something happened or find a certain place. (F)
Collaboration	Consortium-type blockchain is a great solution because it allows predefined groups of organizations to manage the network while ensuring data protection and effective collaboration between trusted countries. (A) Blockchain ensures direct and reliable payments between countries. (B)
Understanding the speed of transactions as operational excellence	
Efficiency Gains	Blockchain is capable of processing international transactions way faster than the traditional system despite all the challenges that it had in the past. (J) The most effective is where it is possible to fully automate the process from a to z and where there are no human processes or human intervention. (G) Private networks can be better tailored to specific business needs, so they tend to more effectively address operational challenges such as scaling up the network and the speed of transactions, since they do not have to handle the amount of transactions that are typical of public networks.

	The need for logistics coordinators is decreasing, as blockchain technology makes it possible to monitor cargo more efficiently, dispelling the need to use third parties. (D)
Compliance	Partially private networks can enable companies to comply with legal requirements and regulations by providing a certain level of openness while maintaining the necessary security measures. (G) Certification and quality inspection agencies may also face demand, as all the details are stored on the blockchain network (D). The same applies to customs and to companies associated with customs. (F)

Table 3. The implementation challenges of blockchain adoption frame (coding)

First order codes	Selected evidence
Awareness of system and network integration	
Complexity and risk management issues	When we think about the technology adoption and the multinational company and definitely we have a lot of IT systems, there is a huge complexity of IT infrastructure. So that is definitely there the legacy system. Converting a huge legacy system, which is serving maybe millions of people, making any small change in such a system comes with its own risk that people do not want to do. The risk is too high. (K) So the risk part is massive and when it comes to the IT implementation, it is just not the implementation. You need to think about the impact on the outer society because, for the users, it is not IT. For users, it is, for example, the train coming on time, and for the government, it is to ensure the smooth operation for their civilians. So think of the chain effect. (J)
Network interoperability issues	Network interoperability has a huge effect.(J) The problem of interoperability is one of the most challenging now, let's add up the different data formats, the different security and privacy protocols, necessary to combine smart contracts to be secure and private, and so on.(A) To replace existing systems with blockchain-type solutions would make the process even more difficult for international organizations in particular, and this is one of the reasons where the potential is perceived to be high, but the level of adaptation is still very low. (B)

Security issues	Blockchain networks yet cannot simultaneously provide the three most important features: decentralization, security, and scalability. Security risk is another important challenge yet because software errors or vulnerabilities can lead to data leaks or unauthorized access. Blockchain can also have cybersecurity risks and requires to developed safeguards and a continuous system update policy to avoid potential security vulnerabilities and data vulnerabilities.(D)
Concerns about implementation costs	
High investment cost	High investments required to setup network, support, training, integration, to process change and infrastructure. Since blockchain is very different in terms of storing, processing and sending the data back to the outer layer, it it's a large scale implementation. Why it's quite difficult to implement? So it is time taking. So when it is time-consuming, if you convert that time into dollar value, dollar amount, that's expensive at the same time. (J) Initial investment in technological infrastructure and system integration can be very high, making it particularly difficult for smaller or financially weaker companies. (C)
Governance issues	It's also challenging to shift the mindset towards decentralized autonomous things, organizations, or authorities, or this Consortium mechanism, that keeps the blockchain running, the blockchain infrastructure, which needs to regulate itself. (N) When discussing a private network, specifically a private blockchain that a company has established for itself and its suppliers, we cannot ignore the issue of trust. This issue can only be mitigated by utilizing infrastructure that is not owned by anyone. (G)
Redesign of Business processes	Also, blockchain has its own technological cost, decentralization costs money and changes business processes. (A)
Replaceability	However, this presents another challenge: such infrastructure comes at a cost, it is not easy to replace and you would need to pay for it using cryptocurrencies rather than traditional money. (G) Also, blockchain has its own technological cost, decentralization costs money and changes traditional processes. And as you know, it is very difficult for people to give up what they are used to, even if they see that there is something better. (A)
Transparency demands	Ambivalent demands for transparency Unfortunately, transparency or irreplaceability is not an aspiration for everyone. For some, the opposite is true, so blockchain can be unattractive for them precisely because of these features. (A)

Vague understanding of new phenomena	
Lack of managerial mindset regarding decentralisation	So first of all, most of business people, I would say, still over 90% or 95% of people do not even know how a decentralized system works. And then what are the benefits, and why we should go into the decentralization mode? (J)
Lack of the developer's mindset regarding the decentralised systems	It is much easier to teach young people to become blockchain developers than to find a senior developer and try to pivot towards blockchain technologies, because when you find a really good Java developer, he already has this centralised development mindset. And it's really, really tough to switch a mindset of a professional towards decentralized or a synchronous development, because that's totally different approach on all the levels (N)
Fear of a lack of proper competencies	
Lack of managerial competence to understand blockchain based business models	But management people who are doing business right now, they're not always understanding. (J)
Lack of technological competence to build the blockchain technology-based solutions	Technological knowledge, and competencies needed to integrate blockchain with the existing IT systems. We started seeing that there was a problem with getting competent people. <..> we really lack software developers, blockchain developers here. (N) IT people, they are more or less really understand the system, how system works, how IT develop and architecture works.
Association of new technology with uncertainty and risk	
Organisational resistance to change	And also in startup companies, you will see a lot of young stars, young blood is are coming. If you compare with larger companies and look at the management group, they are in their 50s and in their 60s. So it is more like human psychology. They want to be settled. They do not want any more disruption problems. (J) So, in established companies, we have IT information technology or cybersecurity officers who really have a lot of experience. So they do understand. And it looks like they are more capable to understand all the peculiarities or benefits of blockchain technology, but it seems like they are not willing to. So experience is a double-edged sword; it gives you a lot of caution when not to go and when people know where not to go. (K)

Perceived risk in decision- making	<p>So, for larger systems <..> the decision-making sometimes goes up to the politicians. But for smaller scale companies it goes up to the management. I don't see this type of implementation that can be decided by anywhere at the middle level or lower level managers. So since it is highly disruptive in terms of technology, how data stored, specially when it comes to the public data, it is so sensitive how it is stored, how it is distributed, how secure it is and what can be the future implication of storing such data in a non traditional system. That gives a lot of fear to the common people, to the management, those who do not deeply understand the technology, they just do not want to get into something that they do not know. It is like an unknown risk that they do not know, right? Educating the management on blockchain is another thing. (J)</p> <p>Getting approval for any disruptive idea or project is even more difficult in in larger companies. (K)</p>
Fear of opportunistic behavior due to a lack of regulation	
Legal requirements	<p>Scam projects will be always here, that just, you need to do education of your investors, educate your contributors, that is more important thing (N)</p>
Regulatory uncertainty	<p>The digital currency created by Ripple Labs and XRP Ledger is now widely getting popular popularity, even though it went through some legal challenges in the United States itself. So it has its challenges on the legal side but technology wise it is great. (J)</p> <p>The market still lacks the standardisation and regulation necessary to ensure the stability of the technology and its compatibility between different industrial sectors and countries. (B)</p>

Table 4. The Technology Opportunities of Blockchain adoption framing (coding)

First order codes	Selected Evidence
Belief in the significant potential of technology in different industries	
Increasing technology acceptance in mainstream business	<p>I see blockchain coming to the mainstream business. (I)</p> <p>The digital currency created by Ripple Labs and XRP Ledger is now widely getting popular popularity (J)</p>
Technology acceptance in different industries	<p>First of all, it is very suitable for financial management, as it allows you to make fast and secure payments and financial transactions between different countries.<..> In the field of document</p>

	management, the blockchain automate and ensure the authenticity and immutability of documents such as contracts or licenses. (C)
Belief in the innovation potential of technology	
Innovation in Business Models	In supply chain management, blockchain ensures visibility for all transactions, from the purchase of raw materials to the delivery of the final product to the consumer, reducing fraud and optimizing logistics processes. (C)
Sustainability Gains	In business there's that human error of theirs all the time. It's kind of a factor that, again, blockchain helps minimize. Why because there's a traceability of actions all the time, knowing that there's no way to change those records or somehow adjust it to others without knowing it's in it (G)

Table 5. Perceived Ecosystem Readiness Frame (coding)

Perceived Ecosystem Readiness framework	Explanation
Ambivalent perceptions of ecosystem readiness	
Stakeholders Engagement and competencies within the ecosystem	In 2015-2016, I started Meetups here locally <..> and we started talking about blockchain. <..> we started the association together. And basically, then we started the education part (N). Being a Chief Information Security Officer around 2014, I started trading crypto, and then I tried to understand what it is because when you trade, you need to understand what lies behind it, and I started digging deeper into the blockchain and crypto economy. (N) When we started, <..>we had brainstorm, and we used to tell everyone that if there are cryptocurrencies, then we weren't going to be a very easy jurisdiction, certainly not. (O)
Market readiness	But when it goes to the market, and then our customers are taking it to the marketplace for user penetration, that is where the main challenges are coming from. (J)
Institutional readiness	I don't think the government is quite ready for blockchain adoption. (J) We [supervisory institution] had a little analysis of the situation in the countries around us there, and when it was in 2019, we were already made proposals to ammend the Law on the Prevention of Money Laundering and Financing of Terrorism, and we regulated that. <..>We also amended the law and regulated the activities of the ICOs. (S) Now you see like even though it started with challenges, it went to the lawsuit and everything, but how banks are accepting

	<p>them (Defi) in their mainstream operation because of the efficiency of the transaction processing and the amount of transaction it can make per second. (J)</p> <p>We were the first in the regulation of cryptocurrency exchange offices, and specifically, we tried to be the first in the world. We were the first to implement Minivol recommendations in practice. What they recommended, we were already prepared legal acts for legislation (O)</p> <p>We also tried to negotiate with the Government institutions, who should supervise this sector, but there was a great reluctance, nobody wanted to supervise it, and we didn't want to be responsible for this sector, because we understand that blockchain ideology is that there is no centralized institution of some kind, no centralized governance, and that it should be out of control, let's call it that. It is very difficult to control and supervise such a thing, which is designed to be out of control. This is why we initiated, and all our other partners were very reluctant to regulate it, and it got to the point that we remained in charge of that. &lt.>There were also positions from the Bank of Lithuania, that those who have access to that fiat currency should not have access to virtual exchange offices either (S).</p>
<p>Ambiguity around organizational leadership and accountability</p>	
<p>Lack of a dominant type of blockchain</p>	<p>I see blockchain coming to the mainstream business. The digital currency created by Ripple Labs and XRP Ledger is now widely getting popular popularity (J)</p> <p>While onboarding and adaptation to these technologies are not overly complicated, currently, there is no good solution in the market. The lack of it makes it difficult to abandon centralized infrastructures in favour of decentralized solutions. So the problem of distrust among parties is multifaceted and complex. (G)</p>
<p>Regional dominance concerns</p>	<p>Now, all those integration tools depend not on the company decision itself, but on how those integration tools will manage the power they will have. If companies decide to use integration tools, they are now widely available, and all those tools that now cost nothing, will be charged later on, because they will be dominant in the market. Right now it costs nothing, but again prices are coming up will be dominant." (E)</p> <p>Indeed, we [supervisory institution] saw that everywhere there it was a rapid fundraising, that ICOs of Lithuanian origin are very active and attracted a lot of money from the entire world. But when we started to analyse, we saw that most often, if they are legal entities and attributed to Lithuania, then most often they have registered their legal entity in Switzerland, the Virgin Islands, Estonia, in different countries, but there some of these shareholders were Lithuanians. (S)</p>

Fear of harmonisation challenges	
Lack of pressure to adopt blockchain technology solutions	<p>Then there are organizations and there are people, those who are not big proponent of decentralization because on one side it will give you a lot of clarity. But then there are systems and organizations where they do not want clarity. So there comes the policy level changes and challenges. So we need to understand how much of that people really want transparency. When you have the data centralized, you can do manipulation of data because it is in at a single node, you can change, you can manipulate that data, you can show the way you want to show to the end user. But if it is decentralized, that data manipulation part is completely gone. And now think about the people, those who are controlling larger organisations, decision makings, even countries. Do they want that level of not having the power to change anything? Probably no. (J)</p> <p>Unfortunately, transparency or irreplaceability is not a desire for everyone. For some, the opposite is needed, so blockchain can be unattractive for them precisely because of these features. (A)</p>
Unequal digitalisation level within the supply chain	<p>Definitely, I see the reason why blockchain can be a better suit for [logistic companies] as a solution. <.> Why are they not investing in the</p>
	<p>blockchain solution yet, they have more rudimentary problems to solve before coming to that sophisticated problems be solved by blockchain. For example, when the border crossing is happening, the automated calculation for GST taxes, the automated harmonization, these are not even in the place, the harmonization is a big, big part of cross-border. In some countries it is still going through the manual process of hundreds of pages of Excel files. So first those things needed to be automated (J)</p>
Sustainability concerns	<p>The board should be deciding which blockchains are really stable or which are reliable so far. We do not know whether it is a secure technology or whether it is a technology that will sustain for another 100 years. Because for any large-scale implementation, we need to think forward for 5-10 years term not less (J)</p>
Concerns about red tape rigid mentality	

<p>Institutional openness to explore blockchain technologies</p>	<p>After that, there were also initiatives to test innovative technologies with us (in Central bank) a blockchain project, it's in principle, well, we implemented everything. Well, not 100% , but only 80 % of that, we accomplished everything we had planned to do. (P)</p> <p>And all the time they used to say: "we don't have the competences of financial technology", "we don't have a blockchain competency", "we don't have the competences of cryptocurrency". I say- look, let's take one person, let's invest for three months – anyway there are no those competencies, so in three months he will be the number one. And really, we develop a very good people (O)</p> <p>It's a bit of a schizophrenia, they declared to support innovation, startups are ahead, but in fact that it's regulation that kills a lot of innovations, affect business activities investments and so on. (T)</p>
<p>Regional openness towards acceptance of disruptive technologies</p>	<p>[As a regulator] I read and wondered what was going on in the world, and I saw where and what all of the regulations and the dispositions were going to, and the examples of other countries gave me the strength to believe in what I was doing. (R)</p> <p>Since we do business both in EU, United States and Canada, we see the difference between the progressive mindset and the traditional government mindset. So, making the traditional mindset people have about progressive technology easier to understand is a very difficult challenge, and navigating the red tape in the government system is even more difficult. So businesses, they do not want to enter into that zone at all. All they want is smooth operation, good relation with government entities and then making profit at the end of the day. (J)</p> <p>That conservative banking environment is very difficult, not compatible with startups, from the simple things that just if a foreigner invests in a startup, it is challenging to open an account in a bank for a startup, to more specific questions, if a startup gets into some area of blockchain there, that is, a full stop or a ban. (T)</p>